

Air propeller drive from gearbox, combining gas turbine and electrical engines

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to review of one of the ACARE Flight Path 2050 goals (Challenge 3) to develop hybrid turboelectric propulsion (HTEP) in order to reduce the impacts of emissions on the environment.

The paper describes the methods, used to build the core element of the HTEP demonstrator - gearbox, that combines a gas turbine power (GTE) and electrical engine (EE) to drive the propeller as well as to check the gearbox parameters during the test bench run.

The operating modes of the HTEP were analyzed, as well as their interaction of combined gearbox with the GTE and EE. As a result, several combined gearbox schemes were designed.

A research of various combining gearbox schemes was carried out and the choice of its optimal scheme was made from the point of view of minimization of weight-size parameters, self- cost manufacturing costs, while meeting the conditions for ensuring failure free operation during the specified service life. The conducted research is a basis for the preparation of gearbox demonstration model and test programs to fulfill the tasks set in EFACA project.

These results are based on research within of the EFACA project (Environmentally Friendly Aviation for all Classes of Aircraft) which is funded by European Commission through the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant agreement № 101056866), inserted on the Climate, Energy and Mobility cluster. EFACA intends to promote a development aviation sector greener and environmentally friendly with a development of new technologies by using electric and hybrid thermoelectric propulsions and new sustainable fuels aiming at fighting climate change by 2050 (www.efaca.eu).

1. Introduction

The EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 – an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal [1].

The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere is a primary means of support of the planet thermal balance that allows to stop the processes of the global heating and consequentially the catastrophic changes of the climate. Air transport is one of the elements that influence on greenhouse gas emissions. Programs to reduce of a harmful impact of aviation on environment are developed in accordance with strategic approach approved by the ACARE (SRIA. CHALLENGE 3. Environmental protection and energy supply). Within these areas, it has been determined that for future regional aircraft it is rational to use a hybrid turboelectric propulsion (HTEP) by using fuel cells (FC). [2].

Similar programs were also adopted in the USA and the UK – Jet Zero Strategy [3], CORSIA, NextGen, ZVE [4]. Previously, the basic principles for reducing emissions and noise from civil aviation were formulated by ICAO in 2016 [5] and NASA in 2019 [6, 24, 25].

The use of HTEP will allow to reduce greenhouse gases emissions due to the following factors as: optimization of gas turbine engine (GTE) flight cycle, decrease of specific fuel consumption in all flight modes by adding power from electrical engine (EE); or eliminating CO₂ emission using hydrogen as a fuel for the GTE and FC. The creation of the HTEP satisfies the ACARE task: 3.2 Develop air vehicles of the future. New propulsion schemes allow for a

significant reduction in environmental impact and energy consumption. These goals are achieved by increasing the electrical power in a hybrid propulsion. [7]

The European Commission funds the Horizon Europe Programme, one of the main areas is the greening of aviation, i.e. the reduction of harmful substances emissions, C, CO, CO₂, NO_x and others, as well as the replacement of fossil fuels, as a result of which by 2050 emissions should be reduced by 50% compared to 2005. In addition, electric propulsions reduce noise levels.

The EFACA project plans to undertake the preliminary design of hybrid turbo-electric propeller drives for regional aircraft with a capacity of up to 80 passengers and a range of up to 1 000 km, as well as the study of several schemes of electrical engine power supply, including the use of fuel cells.

One of the EFACA work packages involves the creation and testing of the HTEP demonstrator. The demonstrator has a gearbox that sums the drive power from the gas turbine and electrical engines.

2. The current state of electric drive in the aviation

The calculations demonstrate that electric aircraft propulsion must have EE with power to weight ratio 13 kW/kg. At a current time, many companies came close to these criteria.

Wright Electric Company demonstrated a 1 MW reversible electrical engine - generator in 2023. The engine has been already tested in NASA NEAT flight laboratory in the altitude up to 12 000 m. In 2024, tests of the 2.5 MW engine (WM2500) began.

Electrical engine WM2500 is developed by Wright Electric Company for a 100 seat class aircraft under the US government ARPA-E program. It is planned to test it on Bae146 and C-130 aircraft [8].

Honeywell International's Aerospace Technologies division has developed a 1 MW turbogenerator [9].

Zero Avia company (UK) tests ZA600 aircraft, developed on the basis of Do228 aircraft with engines power of 600 kW and FC, and started working on the ZA2000 based on DHC Dash 8 with engines power of 2.0-5.4 MW and FC [10].

magniX Company (USA) has developed electric propulsion unit (EPU) with a frequency 2 300 rpm and direct drive propeller with a power of 350 kW and 700 kW and drive specific power with power source 2.7 и 3.4 kW/kg respectively. The EPU is a permanent magnet synchronous engine powered by an 800 V AC inverter.

In 2019, the first flight of an aircraft with the magniX 500 EPU with a specific power of 3 kW/kg took place. In 2022, the R44 helicopter with the magniX 250 EPU took its first flight.

In 2025, magniX announced the Heli-Storm family of electric engines, which are lighter than gas turbine engines. Designed for small single-engine helicopters and larger hybrid twin-engine aircraft, Heli-Storm engines operate at 6 000 to 7 000 rpm. The first available engine weighs just 75 kg but has a power output of 330 kW [11].

Evoluto Ltd (UK) has developed a range of electrical engines with axial flux. The D500 engine has achieved a specific power of 12 kW/kg. The engine power is 350 kW at 6 000 rpm, which allows for a reduction in the weight of the propeller drive [12].

Fuel cells (FC) have been previously used as auxiliary power units (APU) in aircraft, for example, on the B-737, and the efficiency of fuel cells is 3 times higher than that of a gas turbine APU, and amounts to 40...50%. [13].

MTU Aero Engines, within HEROPS project (Hydrogen-Electric Zero Emission Propulsion System) launched in 2024, are developing fuel cells and a 1,200 kW electrical engine for aircraft propulsions. In particular, the 600 kW electrical engine has a specific power of 15 kW/kg, the fuel cells have an efficiency of 50 [14].

The HORIZON EUROPE project is developing fuel cells with the aim of providing electricity by 2030:

- resource 30 000 h (it has 20 000h),
- efficiency – 50 % (it has 45 %),
- system reliability – 98 % (it has 95 %),
- rated temperature - ≥ 120 °C (it has 90 °C).

The specific capacity of the fuel cell is expected to increase by 45%

Advanced fuel cells with Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) provide an operating temperature 130 – 180 °C, efficiency up to 65% and specific power up to 2 kW/kg [11,15, 16, 17].

The specific power of the FC reaches 2.5 kW/kg, which is reduced almost by 2 times due to secondary design elements. By 2050, it is expected to increase the specific power by 2 times for low-temperature FC and by 3 times for high-temperature FC [22, 23, 26].

A hybrid electric propulsion can have specific characteristics comparable to a turboprop engine (TP), but the reliability of the electric drive and the specific mass of electric power sources are still insufficient for mass operation, so hybrid turboelectric propulsions are preferable.

Diamond Aircraft introduced the first aircraft with a hybrid piston-electric propulsion, the DA36 E-Star, in 2011. A 70 kW Siemens electrical engine turns the propeller and is powered by electricity from a generator driven by a 30 kW

Austro Engine Wankel engine and a battery. This hybrid propulsion allows for a 25% reduction in specific fuel consumption [18].

Further development of electrical engine and fuel cells has shown that the all-electric drive is competitive with the gas turbine, at least for local airline aircraft. Work on hybrid propulsions continues, including in the EFACA project. The project involves the creation and testing of a hybrid turboelectric propulsion capable of operating in three propeller drive modes: from a GTE, from an EE, from a GTE + EE, with the EE powered by kerosene-air fuel cells and the GTE powered by kerosene.

In 2018, the German Aerospace Center (DLR) worked on 5 variants of the DLR-127 gas turbine propulsion based on the PW127 turboprop for the ATR-72 aircraft. An additional electric drive powered by batteries was considered, while the hybrid drive was used only during take-off and climb. It was found that with the existing specific power of the battery electric drive components, only a hybrid propulsion scheme with an electric drive with a power of 10% of the gas turbine engine (hybridization 10%) is justified, while the aircraft payload is reduced by 23%, and the emission reduction is only by 10%, while an emission reduction of more than 21% is necessary [19].

At the AIAA AVIATION forum in 2021, research conducted in France on the hybridization of the ATR-72 aircraft propulsion was presented, with fuel cells considered as the source of electrical energy. The results of the German and French research studies are summarized in Table 1. It is obvious that fuel cells have a significant advantage in terms of fuel efficiency and emissions, and this advantage is increased with increasing flight range. The main disadvantage of fuel cells is the need for a powerful cooling system, the mass of which is comparable to the mass of the elements themselves, while the specific power of the fuel cells decreases from 2.5 kW / kg to 1.1 kW / kg max. Improvement of fuel cell characteristics is possible due to high-temperature elements of the HT-PEM type. With the existing characteristics of the electrical system components, the optimal hybridization value for fuel cells can be considered 20%, for batteries 10%; however, at 10% the necessary reduction in emissions is not achieved. [20].

As an alternative to traditional heat exchangers, fuel cells are considered promising SHX heat exchangers from Liebherr Aerospace, which have reduced aerodynamic drag and drag reduction systems due to the jet thrust of the cooling air flow and a system with a phase transition heat pump. [21].

Table 1: Analysis of the hybridization degree of the ATR-72 aircraft power plant

№	Air propeller drive option	Hybridization degree, %	Power, kW		Propulsion mass, kg						Specific power, kW/kg	Mass increase, kg/%	Number of passengers/%	Emissions	Fuel economy	
			GTE	EE	GTE	EE	Gearbox	Electric system	Electric power source source*	Total mass					kg	%
1	Initial ATR72/PW127	0	1 800	0	480	-	-	-	500	980	1.84	0/0	72/100	100	-	-
2	Electric drive/battery	100	-	1 800	0	120	100	310	7 380	7 910	0.23	6 930/1 540	0/0	0	500	100
3	Electric drive /FC	100	-	1 800	0	120	100	310	1 640	2 170	0.83	1 190/121	48/67	0	150	35
4	Hybrid GTE+EE /battery	10	1 600	200	330	14	150	24	742	1 260	1.43	280/29	66/92	95	9	2
5	Hybrid GTE+EE /FC	10	1 600	200	330	14	150	24	620	1 138	1.58	158/16	69/96	90	20	5
6	Hybrid GTE+EE / battery	40	1 100	700	150	47	150	118	1 563	2 028	0.89	1 048/107	50/69	20	36	9
7	Hybrid GTE+EE /FC	40	1 100	700	150	47	150	118	730	1 195	1.5	215/22	68/94	90	20	5

* Mass of energy sources including cooling system

3. HTEP demonstrator

3.1 General position

In accordance with the tasks in EFACA project Ivchenko-Progress JSC must develop and test the HTEP gearbox demonstrator on the test bench.

The HTEP is a gas turbine engine with free turbine (FT), in which the propeller gearbox is driven from the FT and from the EE in parallel or in series.

The HTEP demonstrator is designed to study the characteristics of the propulsion in the test bench conditions, including measuring the torque and torque dynamics, power and thrust of the air propeller (AP), vibrations, noise, emissions and stresses in the propeller shaft in all power modes and drive connection modes. Cases of switching on and off one of the drives, including emergency ones, should be studied as well.

In order to reduce the time and cost of creating a demonstrator, a serial GTE was selected, taking into account the GTE parameters required for the project, as well as the cost of work on the manufacture of additional units of the HTEP and the modification of the test bench.

As a prototype of the demonstrator, the AI-450C-2 turboprop (TP) with a take-off power of 750 hp (550 kW) and an AI-P800V7 air propeller were selected. The turboprop engine and AP are of our own design and manufacture.

A preliminary analysis of the HTEP options was performed similar to the DLR analysis, the results of which are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Aircraft propulsion with two TP/EE/HTEP for a distance up to 360 km

№	Air propeller drive option	Hybridization degree, %	Takeoff power, kW		Mass, kg										
			GTE	EE	GTE	EE	Gearbox	Electric system	Energy source*	Total mass	Specific power, kW/kg	Mass increase, %	Payload, %	Emission decrease, %	Fuel efficiency increase, %
1	TP AI-450C-2	0	660	0	190	-	-	-	150	340	1.94	0	100	0	0
2	EE	100	0	660	-	66	30	90	550	732	0.9	115	69	100	35
3	HTEP – AI-450C-2 + 20% EE	20	550	110	160	11	10	45	125	350	1.88	0	100	20	9
4	HTEP - AI-450C-2 +40% EE	40	440	220	125	22	10	30	210	395	1.67	16	93	40	17

* Taken into account cooling system

3.2 Demonstrator schemes

Several demonstrator schemes based on the AI-450C-2 engine were considered, presented in the figures: 1, 2, 3, 4.

3.2.1 HTEP demonstrator with a free turbine shaft drive from an electrical engine

The HTEP demonstrator based on the AI-450C-2 engine, in which the free turbine shaft (FT) is connected to the EE shaft (Figure 1). In the original engine, the free turbine and exhaust device are modified. The drive from the EE is

provided by a shaft with compensation clutches, which connect the EE rotor through a free wheel clutch (FWC) to the FT shaft.

Advantages - a minimum number of main new parts, about 20, and a minimum total weight.

Disadvantages - an increased risk of fine-tuning high-speed compensation clutches and FWC, a change in the engine mount. Another disadvantage is the rotation of the FT from the EE when the GTE is turned off, which will require blocking the gas-air duct with a damper to reduce ventilation losses.

Figure 1:

3.2.2 HTEP demonstrator with a new gearbox instead of AI-450C-2 gearbox

AI-450C-2 engine gearbox is replaced with a new gearbox which is made according the same kinematic scheme on the Figure 1, but it has additional drive from the EE on the first stage (Figure 2).

Advantages - the scheme has a minimum weight and development risk, high reliability.

Disadvantages - the manufacture of a new housing with the placement of unit drives significantly increases the cost of production. In addition, in this scheme, the FWC operates at a frequency of 39,000 rpm, which reduces its performance.

Figure 2:

3.2.3 HTEP demonstrator with additional cylindrical gearbox

The demonstrator uses a full-size AI-450C-2 engine to which an additional summing cylindrical gearbox is attached (Figure 3).

The kinematic diagram of the AP drive is similar to Figure 2, but the increase of the stages and gearbox casings leads to an increase of the weight and a decrease of the reliability.

Advantages - less labor intensity of manufacture and better reliability of the FWC operating at a frequency of 6,000 rpm.

Disadvantages - an increase in the number of stages and dimensions of the gearbox housings leads to an increase in weight and a decrease in reliability.

Figure 3:

3.2.4 HTEP demonstrator with additional bevel gearbox

The demonstrator scheme is similar to Figure 3.

Advantages - due to the use of a bevel gear from the EE, the mass and dimensions of the summing gearbox are reduced (Figure 4).

Disadvantages - special equipment is required to manufacture non-orthogonal bevel gears.

Figure 4:

3.3 Comparison of demonstrator schemes

The comparison of the demonstrator schemes was performed using the expert assessment method, which is often used at the stage of preliminary design, for example, in NASA [25].

For comparison, the criteria were selected in accordance with the tasks that must be solved during the demonstrator development and testing. Such criteria are:

- Production complexity. The manufacturing costs and preparation for production are estimated.
- Development risk. Increased risk can lead to a violation of deadlines and an increase of the price during the finalization of the demonstrator.
- Reliability. Insufficient reliability leads to an extension of tests and an increase in costs.
- Modification of the test bench. Increasing the volume of modifications to the test bench leads to increased costs.
- Additional mass. An assessment is required to determine the characteristics of the flight version of the HTEP.

The assessment results are given in Table 3.

A comparison of possible demonstrator schemes showed the advantage of Scheme 3.4, with a summing bevel gear. The layout of the flight prototype of the HTEP may differ from the demonstrator due to differences in technical requirements.

Table 3: Assessment results

Scheme (Fugure number)	Production complexity	Development risk	Reliability			Test bench	Additional weight		Rating	
			Parts quantity		Score		kg	Score	Score	Place
	Score	Score	General	Main	Score					
1	5	2	30	20	5	3	20	5	20	2
2	3	3	45	35	3	5	20	5	19	3
3	3	5	45	35	3	4	30	3	18	4
4	4	5	40	30	4	4	20	5	22	1

Notification - rating system (score):

- 5 – Excellent
- 4 – Good
- 3 – Average
- 2 – Poor

4. HTEP demonstrator design

The HTEP demonstrator is a modified AI-450C-2 turboprop engine, in the front part of the gearbox housing of which a summing gearbox is installed, in which the FWC and the propeller shaft are located (Figure 4.1).

A mechanical-hydraulic governor of the AP is installed in the upper part of the front housing of the summing gearbox. The AP governor ensures that the AP rotation speed is maintained at a constant level and that the rotation speed is adjusted depending on the operating mode of the propulsion.

The GTE power is determined using the AI-450C-2 engine gearbox torque; the EE power is determined by the parameters of the consumed current. A magnetolectric scobs alarm, oil pressure and temperature sensors, and a vibration sensor monitor the condition of the gearbox.

Lubrication oil and summing gearbox venting is provided to AI-450C-2 engine oil system. EE has a separate oil system, installed on the test bench.

The AP thrust is determined by a test bench meter.

Figure 4.1: 1- AI-450C-2 engine gearbox; 2- Summing gearbox mounting; 3- Oil pump block; 4- Air propeller shaft; 5- Air propeller governor; 6- Summing gearbox; 7 -Electrical engine.

5. HTEP demonstrator tests

The tests are planned to be carried out according to the program developed based on the typical aircraft flight cycle (Table 4), as well as possible failures (Table 5).

Long-term test programs must confirm the operability of the gearbox as a whole during long-term operation using the equivalent cyclicity method, as well as the operability of the FWC with a resource number of on-off cycles.

Special test programs must confirm the operability of the gearbox in case of sudden failures of one of the drives. In addition, special tests must determine the EE efficiency, the gearbox and EE thermal and vibration state, the AP thrust and noise, as well CO_x and NO_x emissions.

A special test program is used to practice the interaction of the control systems of two drives from GTE and EE, and the propeller.

Based on the results of special tests, an optimal scheme for the propeller control system should be developed in parallel from two drives.

At the first stage of testing the demonstrator, separate control of the GTE and EE is assumed. In this case, the HTEP operating mode is determined by setting the mode of the existing GTE control system and subsequently increasing the mode by connecting the EE, while the HTEP power is determined as the sum of the GTE power, based on torque measurements, and the EE power, based on the parameters of the consumed current. Although such a system complicates engine control, on the other hand, it allows for a prompt response to changes in flight conditions and failure situations.

In the future, an automated control system will be developed, with the power of each drive set by the electronic control system according to a given program or manually.

Table 4: Typical aircraft flying cycle

Flight phase	Engine modes	N_{GTE} , hp	N_{EE} , hp	N_{HTEP} , hp	% $N_{take\ off}$	% n_{AP}
Take off	Maximum Takeoff	750	240	990	110	100
Take off	Take off	750	150	900	100	100
Climb	Maximum continuous, M_{cont} .	660	130	790	87.8	90
Cruise flight	Maximum cruise M_{cr}	640	130	770	86	86
Descending	$0.6 M_{cont}$.	200...400	130	330...530	36...59	86
Landing	Thrust reverse	100	100	200	22	-

Ground	Taxiing	0	150	150		-
Ground	Idle	50-100	0	50-100		-

Table 5: Drive failure imitation on the test bench

GTE - failure	GTE, hp	EE, hp
Take off	0	240
Climb	0	240
Cruise flight	0	240
Reverse	0	200
Taxiing	0	150
EE - failure	GTE, hp	EE, hp
Take off	800	0
Climb	750	0
Cruise flight	640	0
Reverse	200	0
Taxiing	150	0

In addition to the development of the HTEP control system, the tests must include measurements of parameters in accordance with Table 6.

Table 6: Parameters recorded during demonstrator testing

№	Name	Sensor installation location
1	AP rotation frequency	Summing gearbox
2	FT rotation frequency	Free turbine (FT)
3	GTE torque	AI-450C-2 gearbox
4	EE power	Measuring current parameters on the test bench
5	Oil temperature at the inlet and outlet of the EE	Summing gearbox
6	Oil temperature at the inlet and outlet of the gearbox	Summing gearbox
7	AP and EE vibrations	Summing gearbox
8	FT vibrations	Free turbine (FT)
9	AP thrust	Test bench
10	Chips in the oil	Gearbox
11	Noise	Test bench

Because of the demonstrator gearbox tests, the FWC, spline clutches, gear engagements, and bearings must be fine-tuned.

The tests will include fine-tuning of the EE, in terms of increasing efficiency, cooling reliability, as well as the EE control system and the combined control of the EE and GTE.

6 Conclusions

Current state research of hybrid turboelectric aircraft engine components development has shown readiness to begin developing an engine demonstrator test bench.

The HTEP demonstrator is created on the basis of the AI-450C-2 engine with an AI-P800V7 air propeller and tests are planned on a modified IVCHENKO -PROGRESS enterprise test bench. During the tests, an analysis of the operation of the gearbox components with two power inputs - from an experimental EE and a GTE - will be performed, and the engine control system will be debugged. Testing the demonstrator will allow assessing the efficiency of the hybrid propulsion, as well as preparing the basis for flight tests of the prototype.

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